

RESEARCH ON THE ISSUE OF QUESTIONS IN LINGUISTICS

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The concept of interrogation is one of the most common and universal concepts. Science has long been researching the logical properties and characteristics of interrogative pronouns. Interest in interrogation dates back to antiquity. The ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle believed that the main feature of the interrogative pronoun was alternative. According to him, the question arises only when there is an alternative - two ways, that is, the choice of two or more things, and only one of these things can be chosen.

The question is expressed in Chinese in a variety of ways, as in any other language. Therefore, their study requires a deeper understanding of the features of a particular language and a deeper study of its internal structures by comparing and contrasting them with other languages.

"The category of interrogation is a fact of objective reality, which exists in philosophy as well as in language and in speech, that is, it is an interdisciplinary concept. The question category includes time and space, quantity and quality, and many other categories, as well as identifying and disclosing their characteristics."

"Two main approaches can be identified in the study of complex and wide-ranging problems: logical, in which logicians and linguists study the logic of questions, the logic of questions and answers, the communicative-functional theories of question-based reasoning. develop; linguistic, question category problems are analyzed based on a linguistic approach in the study of sentence syntax, in the study of communication theories, in functional-grammatical research, in the study of auxiliary phrases".

According to some logicians, the question is a bridge from ignorance to knowledge. Other researchers say that "due to its paradigmatic nature, it is incorrect to interpret the question as a bridge from ignorance to knowledge, as there is a high probability of refusal or negative response. So the question is a certain contradiction between available and necessary information."

According to PV Chesnokov, "Logical and semantic forms can exist in a constant unity, just as the formation of thinking is two sides of the same process, and this process takes place in one area of linguistic thinking"

"The logic is that every sentence is reflected in words, but not every sentence is a sentence," he said. Judgment is not the only product of thought that can be used as an alternative to speech."

Logicians interpret the question as a form of reasoning, in which the question is not evaluated in terms of truth or falsehood: "The question is such a form of reasoning that it is necessary to determine the validity of a number of judgments and turn them into real reasoning." In the context of linguistic semantics, this can be interpreted as follows: "The main feature of logical reasoning in question is expressed in language in such a way that the content of the interrogative sentence always assumes a certain limit, even if it does not know whether there is a fact in reality." .

Any speech means something, but not everyone confirms something. Whether it is a question or a request, it is all a verbal act in which nothing is affirmed or denied. So, interrogation and pleading are neither true nor false.

We do not see a sharp contrast between the judgment and the message in P.S. Popov's Judgment and Assumption and in P. Tavants's Judgment and Essence. According to P.S. Popov, the interrogative sentences (questions) are in some ways connected with the sentence. They are similar in that they both represent a message. However, the question is the question, and the verdict is the verdict.

N. Belnap, in T. Steele's "Logic of questions and answers" (The logic of questions and answers) writes: "The question is an abstract concept of interrogative. The function of the interrogative is to express the question. A simple question consists of two parts: the subject and the basis. The subject offers several alternatives (choices), and the basis is how many in the answer it determines the amount of real choices and what requirements must be met in response. "

According to I. Hintikka, the only point on which logicians and linguists agree is that "The question is the demander of information. The inquirer needs to be provided with certain information in order to gain knowledge about an event"15. Therefore, the function of the question is not only to convey some information (or part of it), but also to motivate the addressee (respondent) to answer, so that in any interrogative sentence the content of the search for certain information is always hidden.

"Many linguistic works have argued that there is no sharp difference between question, command, and verb, and that the system of visual means of language is the general question of command, the command from the definite, the definite from the general. rock becomes speech. In this sense, FF Fortunatov and later AI Peshkovsky studied interrogative sentences as a type of command sentences"16. According to A.D. Smelev, in everyday life interrogative pronouns are used not only as a question, but also to convey a command, a message17. He goes on to say that "in scientific texts, interrogative pronouns are used as rhetorical

interrogative pronouns, representing the message, not the question." So, from the logical point of view, the interrogation does not represent a true or false judgment. According to linguists, the interrogative sentence is not only a task of searching for information, but also the meaning of the command, the effect of a fact on a fact, or the meaning of the message, which requires verbal action from the interlocutor.

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